

MODERN METHODS OF STUDYING GUM RECESSION (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *The tasks of modern implantology and periodontology include both ensuring successful engraftment of a dental implant and achieving functional restoration of the dentition along with obtaining a highly aesthetic treatment result. To achieve a successful result of surgical intervention in the treatment of gingival recession, it is extremely important to find accurate methods for determining the thickness of keratinized soft tissues of the oral cavity before surgical treatment. Currently, existing methods have a number of disadvantages, first of all, they are invasive and traumatic for the patient. Therefore, an important task is to develop an objective non-invasive method for determining the thickness of keratinized soft tissues before surgical treatment. The article presents literature data describing the most common methods for determining the thickness of keratinized gums before surgical treatment. The review and analysis of literary sources was carried out using keywords on the electronic resources of the Scopus, Web of Science, MedLine, The Cochrane Library, and Russian Science Citation Index (RSCI) databases. Foreign and domestic sources were used to write the review article. In addition to parametric measurements of gingival recession, the results of using modern computer technologies during clinical examination are also of great diagnostic value for the prognosis and prevention of soft tissue recession around the implant. Recently, 3D modeling based on non-invasive methods, such as computed tomography for assessing the volume of gum tissue, has become increasingly widespread in maxillofacial surgery and orthodontics. Measuring the thickness of the attached gingiva is also an important indicator in the diagnosis of gingival recession, which plays an important role in predicting and planning a treatment.*

Keywords: *dental implantation, gingival recession, osseointegration, keratinized gingiva.*

It is important to suggest that for the characterization of the volume of the gum and its tissues, methods are used that allow recreating its three-dimensional structure. For a long time, visualization was performed using serial section reconstruction, which takes a lot of time and is usually possible only on a small volume of material [1].

Recently, 3D modeling based on non-invasive methods, such as computed tomography for assessing the volume of gum tissue, is becoming increasingly widespread in maxillofacial surgery [7] and orthodontics [1]. A statistical computer-assisted approach was applied to planning and performing dental implantation surgery, which increased the accuracy of implant placement by 35.5% [2].

Definitely, digital dentistry emerged and developed inextricably linked with rapidly improving computer technologies, from the first attempts at three-dimensional modeling to new methods of X-ray microscopy and tomography on a synchrotron radiation source, which allow successful analysis of the topology and morphology of various structures, including transplanted collagen matrices [3].

However, these methods still allow creating a digital model of a limited volume. For a more complete assessment of the dynamics of the volume of soft tissues of the gum and the characteristics of the dentition, in 2007 a qualitatively new approach- three-dimensional visualization was proposed.

For the first time, a system of three-dimensional visualization of the face and dentition based on the use of optical scanners (a method for constructing a three-dimensional image of the face and dentition, compared in the correct position relative to each other) was created by Rakovski A.N. et al. [5,8].

In order to obtain three-dimensional dentition, complete anatomical impressions of the upper and lower jaws are taken, plaster models are cast. Then, using a three-dimensional scanner, a plaster model of the dentition with a reference object installed on it is scanned. Without changing the position of the plaster model, the reference object is removed, and the dentition itself is scanned again.

For three-dimensional visualization, a universal scanner Roland LPX-250 is used, the operation of which is based on the point scanning method. A laser beam is projected as a point onto the scanned object (plaster models of jaws and silicone bite registers), while the object itself rotates on a turntable in the scanner's internal chamber, and a three-dimensional surface is reconstructed based on the change in distance from the object to the scanner's rangefinder. The maximum dimensions of the scanned object can reach up to 0.4 m in height and up to 0.2 m in diameter. [9]

For three-dimensional scanning, the Rapid Form three-dimensional model editor program (INUS Technology, Korea) is used. Data on three-dimensional models of jaws are saved in *.style files, which contain information on the coordinates of each surface vertex. Using a three-dimensional model and the Rapid Form program, it is possible to measure such important anthropometric parameters as the mesiodistal dimensions of each tooth, the length of the dental arch, the distance between the canines, between the first premolars, between the molars, the length of the anterior segment according to Korcu's, the length of the apical base, the width of the apical base, etc. After receiving the 3D models of the face and dental arches, they are combined by successive comparisons through reference points. Three-dimensional models of the upper and lower jaws are studied in three planes and at different angles, both in the bite and separately for each jaw [13,10].

It is worth mentioning that a method for accurate reconstruction of the dentition through the integration of external scanned data and CT-based medical images has been proposed, when a plaster model is digitized using a 3D scanner and combined with processed digital models of crowns and roots obtained from computed tomography [11].

Measuring the thickness of the attached gingiva is also an important indicator in the diagnosis of gingival recession, which plays an important role in predicting and planning treatment.

In the scientific work of S.A. Nosova (2016), a method was used to determine the thickness of the gum, which consists of puncturing the keratinized gum with an endodontic file or a thin probe with a stopper previously attached to the instrument. [4]

For clinical measurement of the thickness of the gum, some authors have proposed the use of a periodontal probe. The study was carried out by puncturing within the attached keratinized soft tissues in the area of the hard palate [12]

The author D. Ras Perini developed "Hu-Fredy COLORVUE BIOTYPE PROBE". This method is based on the use of probes with different colors. The use of these tools allows classifying the biotype into thin, medium, thick and very thick.

Additionally, in the study of M.A. Akhmatova, A.M. Frolova (2018), a method was proposed for determining the thickness of attached soft tissues by puncturing soft tissues with an endodontic file, size ISO 0.10, with a stopper under application anesthesia Sol. Lidocaine 10%. Next, using a sterile micro ruler, measure the distance from the tip of the file to the stopper, and then take a macro photo of the measured distance. [1]

Dentists perform visual assessments and measurements of gum recession using periodontal probing to evaluate the depth of recessions and attachment levels. High-resolution photography can document and track changes in gum recession over time. This is often used in combination with clinical assessments. Cone Beam Computed imaging technique provides detailed 3D images of the dental and periodontal structures, allowing for a better understanding of the extent and implications of gum recession.

Ultrasound Imaging: This non-invasive method can be used to visualize the soft tissue structures of the gums and assess the health of periodontal tissues. In research settings, tissue samples may be analyzed to study the cellular and molecular changes associated with gum recession.

Studies are exploring the use of biomarkers in saliva or gingival crevicular fluid to assess inflammation and tissue turnover related to gum health.

These methods can be used individually or in combination to provide a comprehensive understanding of gum recession and its implications for dental health.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that the most complete quantitative characteristics of the gum parameters can be obtained on three-dimensional models of plaster casts scanned using optical scanners. It should be noted that this method has not yet been used in experimental studies, no volume assessment has been performed using 3D modeling, and the data obtained have not been compared with the results of instrumental studies.

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